

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING PHONETIC RHYTHM IN SPEECH DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN WITH SPECIAL NEEDS

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Abstract. *In this article, the effectiveness of using phonetic rhythmic technology for developing oral speech of elementary school students with hearing impairment, who belong to the category of children with special educational needs, is highlighted.*

Keywords: *Article 50 of the constitution Special pedagogy, with special needs, inclusive education, cochlear implant, remedial education, hearing problems, oral light, phonetic rhythm, Rau, Vlasova, Pfaffenrod, comparison table.*

Oral speech is the most convenient means of communication for people, through which a person can express his thoughts, ideas, inner experiences, and in general, it is very important to introduce himself to society and take his place in life is a mental process. The lack of verbal speech causes many other mental processes to lag behind or fail to develop. There is no doubt that such people will develop aggressive attitudes towards others.

Currently, hearing impaired people, who make up a significant part of our society, are deprived of this skill of oral communication. Due to the large-scale reforms being implemented in our country for this category of people, COCHLEAR IMPLANT is being installed in them. A child who has experienced this practice begins to hear some sounds of the environment. But it does not mean that a child with a cochlear implant does not have difficulties in using oral speech when he acquires full speech. Experts in the field know very well that if correctional work is not carried out with a child after implantation, he will not be able to acquire speech.

In our country, the methods created by our scientists who conducted research on the speech of hearing-impaired children are being used in practice.

The technology we are referring to is very effective in children who have recovered their hearing and are ready to acquire oral speech. This technology is phonetic rhythmic, and it is no exaggeration to say that this method is one of the most effective kinesiotherapy methods for children with hearing impairment.

Phonetic rhythmic is a system of movement exercises in which various movements (body, head, hands, feet) are combined with the pronunciation of specific speech material (phrases, words, syllables, sound).

In phonetic rhythmic, speech breath, voice, pronunciation of speech sounds, prosody of speech are also studied. We applied this methodology to primary school students of the 101st and 106th boarding schools of our capital.

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In the developmental experiment of our research, we divided 10 students from the 0-1st grade into the experimental groups A and B of the hearing impaired and 10 of the C and D deaf children. In experimental groups A and B hearing-impaired children, the work was carried out with children 3 times a week in the afternoon. One lesson is conducted face-to-face, the second and third individually.

In the 1st lesson, the vowels "a", "o", "u", "i", "e" were worked on.

Lesson 2 exercises focused on working on voiceless explosive consonants "p", "t", "k".

The 3rd lesson is devoted to voiced explosive consonants, in which work is carried out on the sounds "b" and "d".

The 4th lesson is devoted to voiceless sliding and noisy consonants, in which the formation and development of the pronunciation of "s", "sh", "ch" sounds was carried out.

The 5th lesson was devoted to lip-dental consonants, and worked on the sounds "v" and "f".

The 6th lesson was devoted to voiced sliding consonants and worked on the sounds "z" and "j".

The 7th lesson is devoted to sonorities, work was carried out on the sounds "m", "n", "l", "r".

The 8th lesson is dedicated to the back consonants of the deep tongue, working on the sounds "q", "g", "x".

9th grade deep language working on the back consonant sound, i.e. h sound.

The experiment lasted 13 months, which included approximately 45 academic weeks, with 3 sessions per week with each group. So, 135 hours of testing were conducted with each group. Analysis of the results started from the 1st week of the last 14th month. Group A had 50 hours of training on pronunciation of sounds. The remaining 40 hours were spent working on breathing, voice and articulation exercises and rhythm.

Group B spent about 90 hours of training on the pronunciation of sounds. Based on this, it is worth noting that it is appropriate to conduct training for 1 academic year to form all sounds through phonetic rhythms with weak listeners.

We suggest training with deaf students for 2 school years to form all sounds through phonetic rhythmicity.

We have shown the analysis of the results obtained from the educational experiment in diagram 3.

Diagram 3

At the last stage of our experiment, we compared the results of our control group and the groups selected for the developmental experiment and show them in diagram 4. As can be seen in this diagram, according to 6 signs, the dynamics of growth in our A and B groups is higher than in our C and D groups.

Diagram 4

Diagram 5 shows the periodical analysis of the development of 0th grade deaf students according to 6 signs.

Diagram 5

Therefore, from our side, there is no doubt that there is an effect of developing students' oral speech through phonetic rhythms. We have improved the formative and developing method of pronunciation of sounds proposed by Vlasova and Pfaffenrod. Taking into account the orthoepic rules of the Uzbek language, we were able to develop phonetic rhythmic exercises for deep tongue back sounds q, g, h and vowel sound o. Accordingly, we have created an electronic methodological manual. We have presented this electronic manual to school educators, deaf pedagogues, individual teachers and rhythmic leaders.

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